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IMPROVING MECHANICAL AND BARRIER PROPERTIES OF THERMOPLASTIC STARCH AND POLYSACCHARIDE NANOCRYSTALS NANOCOMPOSITES

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Abstract

Thermoplastic starch (TPS) films were developed with normal maize starch matrix using glycerol, D-isosorbide and 1,3-propanediol as plasticizers. Besides, TPS nanocomposite films were prepared incorporating waxy starch nanocrystals (WSNC) and cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) into the normal maize starch matrix plasticized with glycerol. Both TPS films and TPS nanocomposite films were obtained by extrusion/compression method. Their mechanical and barrier properties were analyzed, as well as their viscoelastic behavior. According to the results the TPS films plasticized with D-

isosorbide presented the highest transparency and the best mechanical and barrier properties, whereas 1,3-propanediol was not suitable as it was lost during the thermomechanical processing leading to brittle materials. Glycerol plasticized TPS nanocomposites were developed by incorporating polysaccharide nanocrystals, either WSNC (0, 1, 2.5 and 5 wt.%) or 1 wt.% of both WSNC/CNC in different proportions, in order to approximate the values to those of D-isosorbide films. The effect of both the type and the content of nanocrystal on the viscoelastic behavior and mechanical and barrier properties were investigated. The results suggested that effective interfacial hydrogen bonding interactions were achieved by extrusion/compression processing, obtaining tensile strength, strain at break and Young's modulus increments higher than 100% for nanocomposites reinforced by only 1 wt.% of polysaccharide nanocrystals, both WSNC alone and also combining WSNC/CNC in different ratios.

Keywords

Thermoplastic starch, extrusion, polysaccharide nanocrystals.

1. Introduction

Starch is outlined as precursor of environmentally friendly and bio-based materials due to its availability from several species, versatility to be modified both physically and chemically, biodegradability and low cost [1]. However, starch shows some important drawbacks that hampers the development of starch-based products, such as the high water sensitivity and the poor mechanical behavior [2]. In addition, plasticized starch suffers recrystallization and retrogradation phenomena that affect the stability of the mechanical properties with time [3]. Therefore, several strategies as chemical modification, crosslinking, polymeric blending, using of different plasticizers and the development of nanocomposites have been proposed in the literature as methods to improve the final behavior of starch-based materials [2,4–6].

As it is well known, when starch is gelatinized using temperature and only water as plasticizer, brittle materials without applicability in the packaging field are obtained. In this sense, the addition of other small molecules capable to penetrate between the starch molecules and form hydrogen bonds with the hydroxyl groups of starch is required to produce a durable thermoplastic starch (TPS) material [7–9]. Due to its availability and the final mechanical properties of the resulting TPS, glycerol is the most widely used plasticizer for starch [7]. In addition, quite research works have employed other polar compounds such as polyols (xylitol, sorbitol, maltitol), amines (urea) or amides (formamide) as plasticizers for TPS [8,10,11] and in a less extent mixtures of plasticizers (urea/formaldehyde, urea/ethanolamine, glycerol/anhydrous glucose and glycerol/citric acid) where synergistic effects may occur [11]. In any case, when the gelatinization is performed in presence of an appropriate plasticizer, the mechanical and viscoelastic properties of the obtained material are improved [3,12], showing increased flexibility and processability similar to common thermoplastic polymers [13]. Indeed, the use of convenient plasticizers facilitates the disruption of starch granules and the destruction of the crystalline domains. During the gelatinization, the existing inter- and intramolecular hydrogen bonds between the amylose and amylopectin chains are substituted by new polymer/plasticizer intermolecular forces increasing the free volume and the mobility of the chains, as well as decreasing of the glass transition temperature (T_g) [13–15]. Hence, the type and content of the plasticizer would be decisive factors that determine the final behavior of starch-based materials [15,16]. In this work, in addition to the common glycerol, D-isosorbide and 1,3-propanediol were selected as plasticizer, which have been previously investigated in few works [3,17–19].

The development of bionanocomposites can also contribute to overcoming the limitations of starch by the addition of nano-sized natural and biodegradable fillers such as nanocellulose, cellulose nanocrystals and starch or chitin nanocrystals [20–24]. It is well known that the effectiveness of the reinforcement would depend on the formation of an active nanofiller/matrix interphase as a result

of the good chemical affinity between them and the correct dispersion of the nanoreinforcement. Cellulose, being the most abundant biopolymer in nature, is made up of β -1,4-linked glucose units. It can be isolated from variety of sources (cotton, wood, bamboo, fungi or industrial and crop wastes), where appeared self-assemble into well-defined architectures at multiple scales, from nano to micro size [21]. Cellulose nanocrystals (CNC), extracted either by acidic or enzymatic hydrolysis, present a rod-like or fibrillar morphology and have been widely studied as nanoreinforcement of different synthetic and natural polymers [22,23,25,26]. For instance, Corsello et al. [26] prepared chitosan/CNC nanocomposites obtaining a good incorporation of the CNC at concentration below 5wt.%, demonstrating that the presence of nanofiller/polymer interactions led to higher surface hydrophobicity, lower water permeability and swelling capacity. In the case of starch, it shows a similar chemical structure compared with cellulose, thus facilitating their strong interfacial adhesion due to the formation of numerous hydrogen bonds [20]. Owi et al. [22] demonstrated that the addition of CNC could improve the behavior of a tapioca starch matrix, increasing the tensile strength and decreasing the water swelling capacity. In addition, Nessi et al. [23] observed that the incorporation of CNC up to 2.5 wt.% into TPS matrix, causes the mechanical reinforcement and reduction of the swelling and the enzymatic degradation of the material. Besides to CNC, starch nanocrystals, isolated from potato, pea or maize, have been also investigated as nanoreinforcements of natural rubber, waterborne polyurethanes and polycaprolactone [27–30]. For instance, Wang et al. [27] concluded that the addition of starch nanocrystals into a waterborne polyurethane matrix led to the increase of the young's modulus and the tensile strength and improve the thermal stability. The synergistic reinforcing effect was investigated in this case by adding together starch nanocrystals and cellulose nanowhiskers in the waterborne matrix revealing the formation of a strong hydrogen bonding network due to the combination of different polysaccharide nanocrystals. Moreover, starch nanocrystals extracted by acidic hydrolysis of the so-called waxy starch, with 2D platelet-like

morphology and crystallinity degree close to 50% [31] showed namely good potentiality as nanofiller of TPS [32–35].

Biopolymer based competitive materials prepared using traditional processing technologies, i.e. extrusion, compression, injection and blowing, choosing the most appropriate method depending on the final application, are necessary in order to contribute to the reduction of the dependence on fossil sources. Indeed, the solvent casting technique is the most widely process used for the development of small size films, mainly in research or lab scale productions [17,18,19]. However, from an industrial point of view extrusion or thermomoulding procedures are much more feasible [17,18,19]. In addition, the extrusion process stands out against solvent casting technique due to its excellent mixing capacity and operational flexibility [39].

Therefore, this work aims the development of extruded starch-based films and nanocomposites with improved mechanical and barrier properties to overcome the limitations of conventional starch-films. Firstly, extruded TPS films adding different plasticizers (glycerol, D-isosorbide and 1,3-propanediol) were obtained. The influence of the type of the plasticizer on the viscoelastic behavior, transparency and mechanical and barrier properties of the films was evaluated. Furthermore, extruded TPS nanocomposites were developed using glycerol as plasticizer with different nanofillers contents (1, 2.5 and 5 wt.% of WSNC), as well as with 1 wt.% of WSNC and CNC combined in different ratios. The nanocomposites were characterized in terms of their thermal stability, mechanical and barrier properties.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Normal corn starch (73 wt.% amylopectin and 27 wt.% amylose) from Sigma-Aldrich was employed to obtain the TPS films. Glycerol (Panreac, 99%), D-isosorbide (Sigma-Aldrich), and 1,3-propanediol

(Quimidroga S.A.) were used as plasticizers (Scheme 1). Waxy corn starch (~0% amylose [1]) and microcrystalline cellulose (both provided from Sigma-Aldrich) were used to obtain by acidic hydrolysis WSNC and CNC, subsequently. For the hydrolysis sulfuric acid (from Panreac, 96%) was employed. Distilled water was used as solvent.

Scheme 1 – Chemical structure of employed plasticizers.

2.2. Preparation of waxy starch nanocrystals (WSNC)

The preparation of WSNC was carried out by acidic hydrolysis according to the method described previously [31,33]. 36.725 g of waxy corn starch were mixed with 250 mL of sulfuric acid aqueous solution (3.16 M) maintaining the reaction for 5 days at 40 °C under continuous magnetic stirring. After that, the reaction was stopped adding distilled water. The suspension was then washed and centrifuged, replacing the supernatant with fresh distilled water until a neutral pH was measured. Finally, the product was freeze-dried, and the WSNC were stored at controlled temperature and relative humidity (22 °C and 10%) until their use. The resulting platelet-like WSNC were 28.2 ± 7.4 nm in width and 35 ± 7.9 nm in length and presented a crystallinity degree of 22.8% [31].

2.3. Preparation of cellulose nanocrystals (CNC)

The preparation of CNC was also performed by acid hydrolysis following the procedure reported in literature [31,40,41]. 5 g of microcrystalline cellulose were treated with sulfuric acid 64 wt.% aqueous solution for 30 min at 45 °C with continuous magnetic stirring. Then, the reaction was stopped adding distilled water. The suspension was washed by centrifugation replacing the supernatant by fresh

distilled water until it became turbid and neutralized by dialysis against distilled water (Spectra Por 12,000 - 14,000 MWCO regenerated cellulose dialysis membranes from Spectrum Laboratories). Finally, the suspension was freeze-dried, and the CNC were stored at controlled temperature and relative humidity (22 °C and 10%) until their use. The CNC showed fibrillary morphology with 9.1 ± 2.6 nm in diameter and 150.6 ± 29.1 nm in length ($L/D = 17$) and a crystallinity degree of 83.6% [31].

2.4. Preparation of thermoplastic starch (TPS)

The TPS films were prepared following a 3 steps procedure: gelatinization, extrusion and compression. The first step consisted on a preliminary gelatinization by heating the mixture of normal corn starch (3.58 g), distilled water (35 ml) and the desired plasticizer (1.93 g) (glycerol, D-isosorbide and 1,3-propanediol) at 90 °C for 20 min [3]. Then, the obtained gel was homogenized using a POLYTRON® PT 2500 E system and finally freeze-dried and stored at 22 °C and 10% of relative humidity. Secondly, the freeze-dried material was extruded using a HAAKE MiniLab extruder at 120 °C and 50 rpm and pelletized. Finally, the material was compressed using a Specac's Atlas Series Manual Hydraulic Press with a temperature controller cell working at i) 120 °C for 5 min without pressure and ii) 120 °C and under a pressure of 2.5 t for 5 min. TPS films with an average thickness of 0.202 ± 0.05 mm were obtained.

The plasticizer content was established in 35 wt.% for all the extruded samples, relative to the starch plus plasticizer total weight. Extruded films were stored at 22 °C and 43% of relative humidity for two weeks before characterization. The samples plasticized with glycerol, D-isosorbide and 1,3-propanediol were named as TPS-X, where X is the type of the plasticizer (Table 1). The manufacturing process for TPS obtained by extrusion/compression process is illustrated in Figure 1.

2.5. Preparation of TPS based nanocomposites

The nanocomposites were obtained using glycerol as plasticizer (35 wt.%) and following the same 3 steps procedure (gelatinization, extrusion and compression) described previously. However, in this case, after the first step and once the gelatinization was completed (90 °C for 20 min), the desired amount of polysaccharide nanocrystals was added, after being homogeneously dispersed in distilled water by ultrasonication. In order to avoid the gelatinization of starch nanocrystals, the mixture was cooled down below 50 °C before adding the nanoreinforcements. The water content used for the dispersion of the nanocrystals was taken into account, in order to maintain constant the final water content of the samples. Thereafter, the protocol was followed out as described above. TPS nanocomposite films with an average thickness of 0.199 ± 0.02 mm were obtained.

The nanocomposites were also stored at 22 °C and 43% of relative humidity for two weeks before their characterization. The samples were named as TPS-GY where Y is related to the nanofiller content. When WSNC and CNC are combined, the WSNC/CNC ratio is indicated in brackets (Table 1).

Table 1. Composition of obtained TPS films and nanocomposite films.

Sample	Plasticizer	Nanocrystal (wt.%)	WSNC (wt.%)	CNC (wt.%)
TPS-G	Glycerol	0	0	0
TPS-I	D-isosorbide	0	0	0
TPS-PD	1,3-propanediol	0	0	0
TPS-G1(100/0)	Glycerol	1	100	0
TPS-G1(50/50)	Glycerol	1	50	50
TPS-G1(0/100)	Glycerol	1	0	100
TPS-G2.5	Glycerol	2.5	100	0
TPS-G5	Glycerol	5	100	0

Figure 1 – Manufacturing process step by step for TPS films and nanocomposite films.

2.6. Characterization methods

TPS films were analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) in order to analyze the changes in the crystallinity of the native starch and assess the effectiveness of each plasticizer to destroy it. Samples were analyzed using a Philips Xpert Pro diffractometer operating at 40 kV and 40 mA. Scattered radiation was detected in the angular range 1 - 40° (2θ).

The optical transmittance of the TPS films was measured by Ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy (UV-vis spectroscopy) using a Shimadzu UV-3600/3100 instrument, operating at room temperature in the range of 400 to 700 nm.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed to study the thermal degradation process of prepared starch-based films. Measurements were performed using a Mettler Toledo TGA-SDTA 851 instrument from 25 to 800 °C, with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ under nitrogen atmosphere.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was carried out using an Eplexor 100N instrument from Gabo Qualimeter. The specimens were cut as a rectangular strip (25 x 3 x 0.2 mm³) and subjected to a 0.05% constant strain recording the storage modulus (E') the loss modulus (E'') and the ratio between the two components (tan E''/E'). Measurements were performed at 1 Hz, working from -100 to 0 °C with a heating rate of 2 °C min⁻¹.

The mechanical behavior of the TPS films and the nanocomposites was evaluated by tensile tests using a Universal Testing Machine Instron 5967. Measurements were carried out at room temperature using a load cell of 50 N. Samples were cut into Dumbbell shaped specimens with a testing section of 5 mm wide, 0.2 mm thickness and 15 mm long. Tests were performed at a crosshead rate of 5 mm min⁻¹.

Water vapor transmission rate experiments of TPS and nanocomposites were performed at 25 °C with a gravimetric cell in which a small amount of liquid water was sealed by the film. The cell was put on a weighting scale with a readability of 10⁻⁵ g and the weight loss of the cell, solely due to the permeation of the water vapor through the film, was registered by means of a computer connected to the scale. The water vapor transmission rate can be defined by:

$$\text{Water vapor transmission rate} = \frac{m \cdot l}{A(a_{\text{int}} - a_{\text{ext}})} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where m is the weight loss of the cell; l is the film thickness; A is the exposed area of film (2.54 cm²); a_{int} is the water activity which is equal to 1 inside de cell and a_{ext} is the penetrant activity outside the cell (assumed to be equal to the relative humidity in case of water). In all cases values of 0.3 of relative humidity (one percent) in the outside of the cell was considered.

Oxygen transmission rate measurements of all films were carried out using a MOCON OXTRAN Model 2/21 gas permeability tester in accordance with the ASTM standard D3985. The oxygen transmission rate of the samples was tested at 760 mmHg, 50% of relative humidity and 23 °C.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of the plasticizer type on the properties of extruded TPS films

The effectiveness of the gelatinization was deduced from XRD patterns and UV-vis transmission values for each TPS. The obtained XRD diffractograms and the UV-vis transmission spectra are shown in Figures 2a and 2b, respectively.

The native corn starch presented several reflection peaks located at $2\theta = 15.2^\circ$, $2\theta = 17.3^\circ/18.1^\circ$ (double) and $2\theta = 23.2^\circ$, that correspond to A-type polymorphism of starch according to literature [42,43]. In contrast, TPS-G, TPS-I and TPS-PD starch materials did not present residual A-type crystallinity related to the remainder crystallinity due to incomplete melting of the native starch crystals [44].

As it could be observed, all samples showed considerably reduced crystalline area in their diffractograms with low intensity residual peaks associated to the processing-induced crystallinity attributed to the crystal structures of single helical of amylose with a complexing agent (plasticizer) inside the helix channel [44,45]. Three processing-induced crystalline structures appeared commonly in processed TPS materials, namely Vh-type, Va-type and Eh-type [18,44]. The developed crystallinity depends on the starch composition, the plasticizer used, the hydrophilic/hydrophobic properties of resulting TPS and the processing parameters [18].

The peak located at $2\theta = 19^\circ$ that appeared in glycerol containing samples that is usually accompanied by another one at $2\theta = 13.3^\circ$, is normally attributed to Vh-type crystalline structure, commonly resulted as a consequence of the shear stress during the thermomechanical processing [17]. However, in the case of TPS-I, the peak was located at $2\theta = 18^\circ$, which is related to the Eh-type crystalline structure, and it is formed generally when starch is processed at higher shear stress than that necessary to form Vh-type. This finding was also observed by other authors [17,18] and could be related to higher shear stresses achieved during the extrusion with TPS-I, as a consequence of

increasing melting viscosity due to the higher molecular weight and voluminous geometry of the D-isosorbide molecule.

Besides, it is worth noting that comparing the extruded films obtained in this work with its counterpart casted films [3], a lower area under the curve was observed for the former, indicating that extruded samples presented a lower crystallinity degree.

Regarding the transparency of the samples, remarkable differences were observed on the transmittance value between the three TPS indicating the notable influence of the plasticizer. As commonly occur, the transmittance value increased in all cases as the wavelength increases [46]. However, films plasticized with D-isosorbide showed much higher transmittance values (65.0%) compared with those plasticized with glycerol and 1,3-propanediol (36.5% and 35.8%, respectively), suggesting higher miscibility between the matrix and the D-isosorbide.

Besides, it is worth noting that the transmittance values showed by melt processed samples were in all cases higher than those obtained in our previous work by solvent casting/evaporation method [3], i.e. 18.2% for glycerol, 16.8% for D-isosorbide and 9.2% for 1,3-propanediol. This fact could be related to the reduced crystallinity observed for the samples by XRD measurements. Moreover, although the transparency of films would be influenced by the thickness [47], the mentioned differences noticed in this study could not be attributable to this factor since the thickness of films obtained by solvent casting were close to those processed by extrusion/compression. Therefore, it could be concluded that the shear stress to which the material is subjected during the extrusion process, resulted in significant improvement in terms of starch/plasticizer compatibility seemed to be achieved due to the thermomechanical processing step, leading to highly amorphous material with enhanced transparency properties.

Figure 2 – a) XRD patterns of normal corn starch and obtained TPS films and b) UV-vis transmittance measurements of TPS films.

TGA was performed in order to study the influence of different plasticizers on the thermal stability of the PLS films. The TG and DTG curves of the resulting TPS films are shown in Figure 3.

Results showed that thermal degradation of TPS films was influenced by the type of the plasticizer. The degradation pattern of glycerol-plasticized starch films under nitrogen atmosphere has been broadly studied and it is generally accepted to involve three main mass-loss steps [33,48], (1) the loss of the humidity (25 - 100 $^\circ\text{C}$), (2) the decomposition of the glycerol-rich phase (100 - 200 $^\circ\text{C}$) and (3) the oxidation of the partially decomposed starch (around 340 $^\circ\text{C}$). In our case, glycerol plasticized samples presented the above mentioned three steps pattern, whereas D-isosorbide and 1,3-propanediol containing films presented some relevant differences.

On one hand, the degradation of TPS-I film proceeded in two steps. The first one near 100 $^\circ\text{C}$ is almost imperceptible due to the reduced moisture content of the sample. After that, the decomposition presented a unique step, which covered the range between 170 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 370 $^\circ\text{C}$. The mass loss related to the plasticizer-rich phase and starch-rich phase would appear together, suggesting that D-isosorbide was effectively integrated in the starch constituting almost one phase. As it could be observed, the films plasticized with D-isosorbide led to a high thermal stability, especially below 260

°C. The chemical structure of the D-isosorbide could form large number of hydrogen bonding interactions resulting in the reduction of the mobility of the matrix and also preventing the early liberation of the plasticizer [18]. The hypothesized hydrogen bonding interactions between the starch and the plasticizers are depicted in the Scheme 2. The results obtained are in agreement with the scarce literature reported for D-isosorbide/starch blends, obtained by extrusion [17,18]. On the other hand, for TPS-PD sample the degradation proceeds in two steps, below 200 °C where the mass loss occurred gradually in a broad range that may include the release of moisture and the degradation of plasticizer rich-phase, and above with the degradation of starch rich-phase that slightly shifted to higher temperatures.

Besides, comparing the results obtained for extruded films with the analogous prepared by solvent casting [31], the former showed a lower mass loss below 250 °C. It is worth noting that even the plasticizer content was the same in all TPS samples, the mass loss related with the plasticizer rich-phase of TPS-PD was considerably lower. According to the literature, the boiling temperature of 1,3-propanediol is 214 °C. However, it has been recently reported that the mass loss started at considerably lower temperatures [3,49]. This fact could be the reason for the lower mass loss detected in the TGA, indicating that during the extrusion/compression of the TPS-PD at 120 °C some of the 1,3-propanediol was evaporated.

Figure 3 – a) TG and b) DTG curves of PLS films.

Scheme 2 – Model of the starch/plasticizer hydrogen bonds in TPS films plasticized with a) glycerol,

b) D-isosorbide and c) 1,3-propanediol.

DMA analysis was performed to evaluate the main relaxation temperatures of TPS films plasticized with glycerol, D-isosorbide and 1,3-propanediol. The normalized storage modulus (E'/E'_g) (where E'_g corresponds to the experimental storage modulus at $-100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and $\tan \delta$ as a function of temperature and the E'_g values are presented in Figure 4 and Table 2. As it could be observed, samples plasticized with glycerol and 1,3-propanediol showed two-step modulus drop related to the relaxation of the plasticizer-rich phase ($T_{\alpha 1}$) and the starch-rich phase ($T_{\alpha 2}$) [50,51]. It could be noticed that the use of glycerol and 1,3-propanediol resulted in remarkable differences on $T_{\alpha 1}$, being around $-70\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for TPS-PD and close to $-50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for TPS-G samples. On the contrary, the TPS films obtained with D-isosorbide presented a different viscoelastic pattern, with a single broad modulus drop at significantly higher temperatures. The results would indicate the existence of a single-phase homogeneous material and would agree with the previous statements regarding the high miscibility between D-isosorbide and starch.

Figure 4 – E'/E'_g and $\tan \delta$ as a function of temperature for TPS films.

Table 2. E'_g values of TPS films at $-100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Sample	E'_g (MPa)
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TPS-G	15227.6
TPS-I	7961.6
TPS-PD	4472.0

The influence of the plasticizer on the mechanical behavior of the extruded films was evaluated by tensile test measurements. The results of all samples are collected in Figure 5 and Table 3. As all samples were stored at controlled temperature/relative humidity before the tests, it could be concluded that the mechanical behavior of the films would be governed by the physicochemical properties of the plasticizer, i.e. molecular weight, chemical structure or hydrophobicity as well as by its ability to form hydrogen bonds with the starch [52].

As expected, the overall mechanical behavior of the material was strongly affected by the plasticizer type and significant differences were observed, mainly in the case of using 1,3-propanediol. Indeed, the TPS-PD film showed the highest Young's modulus and tensile strength values, while presented extremely low strain at break value typical of brittle materials. These results suggest that effective plasticization was not achieved in TPS films plasticized with 1,3-propanediol, which could be attributable to the mentioned loss of 1,3-propanediol during the extrusion or compression steps. On the contrary, the films containing glycerol and D-isosorbide showed better overall mechanical performance. However, comparing both samples tougher and stiffer mechanical behavior was observed for the latter. In fact, the Young's modulus of TPS-I was found to be almost 5 times higher than that for TPS-G with considerably higher values of tensile strength and elongation at break. The better results of D-isosorbide would be related to the numerous hydrogen bonds between the plasticizer and the starch chains [18] leading to the higher strength and strain values.

Figure 5 – Stress vs strain curves of TPS films.

Table 3 – Mechanical properties of TPS films.

Sample	Young's modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Strain at break (%)
TPS-G	12.4 ± 2.1	1.2 ± 0.4	44.6 ± 2.3
TPS-I	55.4 ± 5.3	2.7 ± 0.5	72.4 ± 12.2
TPS-PD	178.6 ± 29.3	3.6 ± 1.8	5.8 ± 3.3

The barrier properties of the different starch-based extruded materials were investigated gravimetrically by evaluating the water vapor and oxygen transport through the films. Water vapor and oxygen permeability, WVP and OP respectively, were calculated according to following Equation:

$$\text{Permeability} = \frac{TR}{\Delta P} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where TR is the water vapor or oxygen transmission rate and ΔP is the water vapor or oxygen pressure difference. TPS-PD sample resulted extremely brittle and, unfortunately, the characterization of its barrier properties was not possible in that case.

As stated by other authors [13,53], in general polysaccharide-based films show high WVP values, whereas they present better behavior against non-polar molecules such as O₂ and CO₂. As it is well known, the transport of gas molecules depends on both diffusion and solubility coefficients [54].

Previous studies conducted for solvent casted equivalent plasticized starch films [31] demonstrated that the WVP was mainly governed by the high ability of water molecules to interact and penetrate through the film because of the strong starch/water affinity, and thus was independent on the quality of starch/plasticizer interactions. It has also taken into account that the plasticizer content is also a critical factor in barrier properties [55]. The results obtained for TPS were similar to those obtained by solvent casting for the same plasticization compositions showing no relevant differences regarding the WVP with different plasticizers. WVP values of $(83 \pm 15) \times 10^{-11}$ and $(109 \pm 37) \times 10^{-11} \text{ g m m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ were measured for TPS-G and TPS-I, whereas values of $(68 \pm 6) \times 10^{-11}$ and $(60 \pm 6) \times 10^{-11} \text{ g m m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ were determined for glycerol and D-isosorbide casted samples, respectively. On the contrary, the OP was again found to be strongly influenced by the plasticizer used, and near twenty times lower OP value was obtained for TPS-I comparing to that obtained for glycerol plasticized one. OP values of 108 ± 35 and $6 \pm 3 \text{ cm}^3 \mu\text{m m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ kPa}^{-1}$ were measured for TPS-G and TPS-I, respectively, higher than the OP values obtained for casted films ($(37 \pm 1) \times 10^{-11} \text{ g m m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ for glycerol and $(5 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-11} \text{ g m m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ for D-isosorbide). Le Corre et al. [56] compared the barrier properties of films prepared with different biopolymers and synthetic polymers. Focusing on those based on starch, it could be concluded that the WVP value is very variable, since it depends on many factors such as the origin of starch the plasticizer type and content and the employed processed and storage conditions. The significant decrease of the oxygen permeability for the D-isosorbide plasticized films could be related to the reduction of the oxygen solubility due to the hydrogen bonding interactions between starch and D-isosorbide, saturating the sorption sites [57].

In summary, comparing the results obtained in this work with those reported for solvent casted films [31], it could be concluded that the thermomechanical processing led to stiffer materials with higher tensile strength values and lower elongation at break value.

3.2. Starch-based nanocomposites reinforced with polysaccharide nanocrystals

As it could be concluded from the above presented results, the final properties of the TPS films strongly depended on the plasticizer. Films plasticized with 1,3-propanediol could be discarded as at high processing temperatures the loss or degradation of 1,3-propanediol occurred, resulting to brittle materials. On the contrary, the use of D-isosorbide led to films with higher transparency, higher tensile strength and elongation values and reduced oxygen permeability comparing to glycerol plasticized films due to the higher amount of hydrogen bonding linkage formed with starch chains.

Therefore, in order to increase the competitiveness of glycerol plasticized films, it was considered that the incorporation of polysaccharide nanocrystals, namely WSNC and CNC, into the glycerol plasticized matrix could led to the improvement of the behavior of the material, especially the one related to the mechanical properties.

The viscoelastic behavior of all TPS nanocomposites was analyzed by means of DMA measurements. The E'/E'_g and $\tan \delta$ as a function of temperature of the nanocomposites reinforced with WSNC and those reinforced by combining both nanocrystals are presented in Figure 6a and 6b, subsequently and the E'_g values in the Table 4. All nanocomposites showed similar viscoelastic pattern compared with that observed for the TPS-G matrix, i.e. they presented the two-step modulus drops associated to the relaxation processes of the glycerol-rich phase ($T_{\alpha 1}$) and starch rich phase ($T_{\alpha 2}$), respectively.

The most remarkable finding of the TPS reinforced with WSNC was the shift of the onset of $T_{\alpha 2}$ to higher temperature values, especially in the case of 5 wt.% content indicating the proper integration

of WSNC in the matrix and the expected effective TPS/WSNC hydrogen bonding interactions. Indeed, it could be suggested that the WSNC were affecting preferably the mobility of the starch-rich phase, revealing strong hydrogen bonding interactions between the WSNC and the amylose/amylopectin chains of the matrix. However, it is worth noting that the intensity of the maximum of $\tan \delta$ of the glycerol-rich phase decreased with increasing amount of WSNC, specially upon the addition of 5 wt.% content, indicating that the addition of WSNC influenced the phases distribution resulting in less plasticizer-rich phase in the material. Although the reported literature with WSNC is scarce, the behavior of the two main relaxations of the glycerol plasticized TPS is in agreement with that reported by Angellier et al. [32].

In a similar way, for TPS nanocomposites reinforced with 1 wt.% of both WSNC and CNC, the glycerol chains that relaxed during the first transition decreased as CNC were incorporated, resulting in a slight decrease of the intensity of the maximum of the $\tan \delta$. Regarding the effect of nanocrystals type, a shift to higher temperatures of $T_{\alpha 1}$ was observed for nanocomposites reinforced with CNC, which could be attributed to the mobility restrictions imposed by high aspect ratio nanocrystals. Concerning the relaxation of the starch-rich phase, although a shift respect to the unfilled matrix was observed for $T_{\alpha 2}$, similar values were measured in all samples reinforced with 1 wt.% WSNC/CNC, being not dependent on the type of nanoreinforcement. Regarding E'/E'_g , similar values were obtained for nanocomposites, independent on the nanocrystals type, but higher than the unfilled matrix, corroborating the reinforcing effect of nanocrystals.

Figure 6 – E'/E'_g and $\tan \delta$ as a function of temperature for a) TPS nanocomposites reinforced with different content of WSNC and b) combining a 1 wt.% of both WSNC and CNC in different ratios.

Table 4. E'_g values of TPS nanocomposites.

Sample	E'_g (MPa)
TPS-G1(100/0)	3800.5
TPS-G1(50/50)	7272.2
TPS-G1(0/100)	5628.8
TPS-G2.5	4267.9
TPS-G5	3712.7

The reinforcing effect of polysaccharide nanocrystals into an extruded TPS matrix was evaluated by tensile test measurements at room temperature. The mechanical properties are summarized in Figure 7. As expected, the addition of nanocrystals resulted in the improvement of the overall mechanical properties of the films.

Regarding the nanocomposites reinforced with WSNC (Figure 7), an increase of the Young's modulus was observed as the WSNC content increased. In addition, the nanocomposites presented significantly higher elongation at break values comparing to the unfilled matrix. This improvement demonstrated the suitability of extrusion/compression to reach a good integration and a good affinity between the matrix and the nanoreinforcement, expected due to their identical chemical

structure, thus revealing strong interfacial interactions that resulted in the effective transmission of mechanical stress [58–60]. It is worth noting that even though upon the addition of 1 wt.% of WSNC the strain at break value slightly trended to decrease, the tensile strength value continued increasing. Thus, it could be concluded that the presence of WSNC up to the used 5 wt.% provided a significant enhancement of the area under the curves, improving the toughness of the films.

Similar tendency was observed with the incorporation of CNCs into the TPS matrix, where higher Young's modulus and maximum tensile strength values were obtained. In fact, when CNC were used as nanoreinforcement, the Young's modulus increased from 17.8 ± 3.6 MPa for TPS-G1(100/0) up to 32.6 ± 7.8 MPa for TPS-G1(0/100) and the tensile strength increased from 1.8 ± 0.2 MPa up to 2.4 ± 0.1 MPa. It is worth to note that the values obtained for the film nanoreinforced with only 1 wt.% of CNC were similar to those obtained when adding 5 wt.% of WSNC. This would be related to the high crystallinity degree of CNC which was demonstrated to be near 80%, significantly higher than that for WSNC (close to 20%) [31]. Besides, the rod-like geometry and the high aspect ratio of CNC facilitated the interactions with the matrix and the effective improvement of the mechanical properties.

Table 5 – Mechanical properties of TPS nanocomposites reinforced with WSNC and combining WSNC/CNC.

Sample	Young's modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Strain at break (%)
TPS-G	12.4 ± 2.1	1.2 ± 0.4	44.6 ± 2.3
TPS-G1(100/0)	17.8 ± 3.6	1.8 ± 0.2	78.6 ± 22.2
TPS-G1(50/50)	27.9 ± 7.0	1.7 ± 0.2	77.7 ± 14.7
TPS-G1(0/100)	32.6 ± 7.8	2.4 ± 0.1	81.1 ± 7.0
TPS-G2.5	23.7 ± 2.9	2.0 ± 0.1	71.9 ± 14.2
TPS-G5	37.7 ± 4.0	2.1 ± 0.2	68.0 ± 2.3

It should be mentioned that comparing the results of films obtained by extrusion with their analogues obtained by solvent casting [31], higher Young's modulus and strain at break values were obtained for those extruded films.

The barrier properties of nanocomposites reinforced with WSNC and both types of polysaccharide nanocrystals were also evaluated by water vapor and oxygen transmission rate measurements. As stated above, the type of plasticizer did not influence the WVP value, being only governed by the starch/water interactions. Moreover, the WVP of the TPS nanocomposites was found to be similar in all cases, around $120 \times 10^{-11} \text{ (g m m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1})$. A comparable tendency was obtained by García et al. [33] for nanocomposites based on waxy maize starch matrix gelatinized with a similar glycerol content and reinforced with WSNC. It should also take into account that the plasticizer content used could be also affecting the permeability value of the nanocomposite, since it has been demonstrated that higher plasticizer contents provokes the worsening of the barrier properties in TPS [55].

Regarding the OP results, it was expected that the increase of WSNC content could led to the decrease of the OP values, due to the capacity of these platelet-like nanocrystals to generate a tortuous path for the O_2 molecules, decreasing the diffusivity, as long as a good dispersion of the nanofiller and appropriate nanofiller/matrix interface were achieved. In this sense, the OP of the TPS with the highest WSNC content was evaluated. A reduction of around 80% in the OP value was seen for the TPS nanocomposite containing 5 wt.% of WSNC, from 108 ± 35 to $20 \pm 3 \text{ cm}^3 \mu\text{m m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ kPa}^{-1}$ for TPS-G and TPS-G5, respectively.

Likewise, when focusing in the TPS matrix reinforced with 1 wt.% of CNC, it was observed that the permeability value decreased due to the incorporation of CNC into the TPS matrix. OP value of $70 \pm 6 \text{ cm}^3 \mu\text{m m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ kPa}^{-1}$ was measured for the TPS-G1(0/100) sample. However, as hypothesized, the WSNC showed greater effectiveness in the decrease of the permeability against O_2 molecules

due to their platelet-shape morphology. Furthermore, it should be pointed that adding 1 wt.% of WSNC, the OP value decreased up to $43 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mm m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ atm}^{-1}$, evidencing the importance of the nanoreinforcement morphology.

4. Conclusions

Firstly, the influence of using either glycerol, D-isosorbide or 1,3-propanediol as plasticizer for corn starch-based films processed by extrusion/compression technique was investigated. As demonstrated, the numerous hydrogen bonding interactions between the D-isosorbide and starch led to the development of TPS films with excellent mechanical properties and reduced oxygen permeability values. The D-isosorbide plasticized films showed a unique relaxation temperature indicating great miscibility with the matrix, which also was reflected in the highest transparency of the films. Regarding 1,3-propanediol containing films, they resulted extremely brittle probably due to the partial evaporation of the plasticizer during the extrusion process, whereas the glycerol presented intermediate overall behavior.

Glycerol TPS based nanocomposites containing WSNC and/or CNC were developed. The DMA results showed that for TPS nanocomposite films, the starch-rich phase was more affected by the nanocrystals, especially for high WSNC contents. In addition, due to the addition of nanocrystals all the nanocomposites exhibited remarkably enhanced mechanical properties in the composition range studied. Effective interfacial hydrogen bonding interactions could be concluded as responsible of the successful toughening of the matrix, especially with the incorporation for highly crystalline fibrillar CNCs, even at low contents. Regarding barrier properties of TPS and TPS nanocomposites plasticized with glycerol, while WVP was governed by starch/water interactions and plasticizer content and was not reduced with the incorporation of polysaccharide nanocrystals, the oxygen permeability was

reduced demonstrating the effectiveness of nanocrystals to create a tortuous pathway, mainly for platelet-like WSCN.

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Data availability

The data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] M. N. Belgacem; A. Gandini, A. J. F. Carvalho, Starch: Major Sources, properties and applications as thermoplastic materials, in: M. Belgacem, A. Gandini (Eds.) Monomers, polymers and composites from renewable resources, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2008: pp. 321–342. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-045316-3.00015-6>.
- [2] F. Xie, E. Pollet, P.J. Halley, L. Avérous, Starch-based nano-biocomposites, Prog. Polym. Sci. 38 (2013) 1590–1628. doi:10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2013.05.002.
- [3] K. González, L. Martin, A. González, A. Retegi, A. Eceiza, N. Gabilondo, D-isosorbide and 1,3-propanediol as plasticizers for starch-based films: Characterization and aging study, J. Appl. Polym. Sci. 134 (2017) 1–10. doi:10.1002/app.44793.
- [4] N. Masina, Y.E. Choonara, P. Kumar, L.C. du Toit, M. Govender, S. Indermun, V. Pillay, A review

of the chemical modification techniques of starch, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 157 (2017) 1226–1236. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2016.09.094.

- [5] J. Waterschoot, S. V. Gomand, E. Fierens, J. A. Delcour, Starch blends and their physicochemical properties, *Starch/Stärke*. 67 (2015) 1–13. doi:10.1002/star.201300214.
- [6] M. Kaseem, K. Hamad, F. Deri, Thermoplastic starch blends: A review of recent works, *Polym. Sci. Ser. A*. 54 (2012) 165–176. doi:10.1134/S0965545X1202006X.
- [7] A. Taghizadeh, B.D. Favis, Effect of high molecular weight plasticizers on the gelatinization of starch under static and shear conditions, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 92 (2013) 1799–1808. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2012.11.018.
- [8] M. Rico, S. Rodríguez-Llamazares, L. Barral, R. Bouza, B. Montero, Processing and characterization of polyols plasticized-starch reinforced with microcrystalline cellulose, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 149 (2016) 83–93. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2016.04.087.
- [9] M. Zdanowicz, P. Staciwa, T. Spychaj, Low transition temperature mixtures (LTTM) containing sugars as potato starch plasticizers, *Starch-Stärke*. 71 (2019) 1900004–1900010. doi:10.1002/star.201900004.
- [10] M. Esmaeili, G. Pircheraghi, R. Bagheri, Optimizing the mechanical and physical properties of thermoplastic starch via tuning the molecular microstructure through co-plasticization by sorbitol and glycerol, *Polym. Int.* 66 (2017) 809–819. doi:10.1002/pi.5319.
- [11] F. Ivanič, D. Johec-Mošková, I. Janigová, I. Chodák, Physical properties of starch plasticized by a mixture of plasticizers, *Eur. Polym. J.* 93 (2017) 843–849. doi:10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2017.04.006.
- [12] P.A. Sreekumar, M.A. Al-harhi, Effect of glycerol on thermal and mechanical properties of

- polyvinyl alcohol/starch blends, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 123 (2012) 135–142. doi:10.1002/app.34465.
- [13] X. Tang, S. Alavi, Recent advances in starch, polyvinyl alcohol based polymer blends, nanocomposites and their biodegradability, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 85 (2011) 7–16. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2011.01.030.
- [14] T. Mekonnen, P. Mussone, H. Khalil, D. Bressler, Progress in bio-based plastics and plasticizing modifications, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 1 (2013) 13379–13398. doi:10.1039/c3ta12555f.
- [15] M.L. Sanyang, S.M. Sapuan, M. Jawaid, M.R. Ishak, J. Sahari, Effect of plasticizer type and concentration on physical properties of biodegradable films based on sugar palm (*arenga pinnata*) starch for food packaging, *J. Food Sci. Technol.* 53 (2016) 326–336. doi:10.1007/s13197-015-2009-7.
- [16] P. Rychter, M. Kot, K. Bajer, D. Rogacz, A. Šišková, J. Kapušniak, Utilization of starch films plasticized with urea as fertilizer for improvement of plant growth, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 137 (2016) 127–138. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2015.10.051.
- [17] D. Battezzore, S. Bocchini, G. Nicola, E. Martini, A. Frache, Isosorbide, a green plasticizer for thermoplastic starch that does not retrograde, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 119 (2015) 78–84. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2014.11.030.
- [18] M.R. Area, M. Rico, B. Montero, L. Barral, R. Bouza, J. López, C. Ramírez, Corn starch plasticized with isosorbide and filled with microcrystalline cellulose: Processing and characterization, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 206 (2019) 726–733. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2018.11.055.
- [19] C. Hernández-Jaimes, M. Meraz, V.H. Lara, G. González-Blanco, L. Buendía-González, Acid hydrolysis of composites based on corn starch and trimethylene glycol as plasticizer *Rev. Mex.*

Ing. Química. 16 (2017) 169–178.

- [20] L. Huang, H. Xu, H. Zhao, M. Xu, M. Qi, T. Yi, S. An, X. Zhang, C. Li, C. Huang, S. Wang, Y. Liu, Properties of thermoplastic starch films reinforced with modified cellulose nanocrystals obtained from cassava residues, *New J. Chem.* 43 (2019) 14883–14891. doi:10.1039/c9nj02623a.
- [21] B. Montero, M. Rico, S. Rodríguez-Llamazares, L. Barral, R. Bouza, Effect of nanocellulose as a filler on biodegradable thermoplastic starch films from tuber, cereal and legume, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 157 (2017) 1094–1104. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2016.10.073.
- [22] W.T. Owi, H.L. Ong, S.T. Sam, A.R. Villagrancia, C. kuo Tsai, H.M. Akil, Unveiling the physicochemical properties of natural *Citrus aurantifolia* crosslinked tapioca starch/nanocellulose bionanocomposites, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 139 (2019) 111548–111560. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2019.111548.
- [23] V. Nessi, X. Falourd, J.-E. Maignet, K. Cahier, A. D'Orlando, N. Descamps, V. Gaucher, C. Chevigny, D. Lourdin, Cellulose nanocrystals-starch nanocomposites produced by extrusion: Structure and behavior in physiological conditions, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 225 (2019) 115123–115131. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2019.115123.
- [24] A.M. Salaberria, J. Labidi, S.C.M. Fernandes, Chitin nanocrystals and nanofibers as nano-sized fillers into thermoplastic starch-based biocomposites processed by melt-mixing, *Chem. Eng. J.* 256 (2014) 356–364. doi:10.1016/j.cej.2014.07.009.
- [25] E. Fortunati, M. Peltzer, I. Armentano, L. Torre, A. Jiménez, J.M. Kenny, Effects of modified cellulose nanocrystals on the barrier and migration properties of PLA nano-biocomposites, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 90 (2012) 948–956. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2012.06.025.

- [26] F.A. Corsello, P.A. Bolla, P.S. Anbinder, M.A. Serradell, J.I. Amalvy, P.J. Peruzzo, Morphology and properties of neutralized chitosan-cellulose nanocrystals biocomposite films, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 156 (2017) 452–459. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2016.09.031.
- [27] Y. Wang, H. Tian, L. Zhang, Role of starch nanocrystals and cellulose whiskers in synergistic reinforcement of waterborne polyurethane, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 80 (2010) 665–671. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2009.10.043.
- [28] H. Namazi, A. Dadkhah, Surface modification of starch nanocrystals through ring-opening polymerization of ϵ -caprolactone and investigation of their microstructures, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 110 (2008) 2405–2412. doi:10.1002/app.28821.
- [29] P. R. Chang, F. Ai, Y. Chen, A. Dufresne, J. Huang, Effects of starch nanocrystal-graft-polycaprolactone on mechanical properties of waterborne polyurethane-based nanocomposites, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 116 (2010) 2658–2667. doi:10.1002/app.
- [30] Y.J.S. Gao, L. Fang, S. D. Li, L. F. Li, S. Q. Liao, Z. F. Wang, Effect of starch nanocrystal on the properties of carbon black-natural rubber composites, *Asian J. Chem.* 26 (2014) 5513–5516.
- [31] K. González, A. Retegi, A. González, A. Eceiza, Starch and cellulose nanocrystals together into thermoplastic starch bionanocomposites, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 117 (2015) 83–90. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2014.09.055.
- [32] H. Angellier, S. Molina-Boisseau, P. Dole, A. Dufresne, Thermoplastic starch - waxy maize starch nanocrystals nanocomposites, *Biomacromolecules* 7 (2006) 531–539. doi:10.1021/bm050797s.
- [33] N.L. García, L. Ribba, A. Dufresne, M. Aranguren, S. Goyanes, Effect of glycerol on the morphology of nanocomposites made from thermoplastic starch and starch nanocrystals,

Carbohydr. Polym. 84 (2011) 203–210. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2010.11.024.

- [34] L. Ren, Y. Fu, Y. Chang, M. Jiang, J. Tong, J. Zhou, Performance improvement of starch films reinforced with starch nanocrystals (SNCs) modified by cross-linking, *Starch/Stärke* 69 (2017) 1600025–1600034. doi:10.1002/star.201600025.
- [35] J. Viguié, S. Molina-Boisseau, A. Dufresne, Processing and characterization of waxy maize starch films plasticized by sorbitol and reinforced with starch nanocrystals, *Macromol. Biosci.* 7 (2007) 1206–1216. doi:10.1002/mabi.200700136.
- [36] C.P.B. Melo, M.V.E. Grossmann, F. Yamashita, E.Y. Youssef, L.H. Dall'Antônia, S. Mali, Effect of manufacturing process and xanthan gum addition on the properties of cassava starch films, *J. Polym. Environ.* 19 (2011) 739–749. doi:10.1007/s10924-011-0325-1.
- [37] M.C. Galdeano, M.V.E. Grossmann, S. Mali, L.A. Bello-Perez, M.A. Garcia, P.B. Zamudio-Flores, Effects of production process and plasticizers on stability of films and sheets of oat starch, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 29 (2009) 492–498. doi:10.1016/j.msec.2008.08.031.
- [38] J.O. De Moraes, A.S. Scheibe, A. Sereno, J.B. Laurindo, Scale-up of the production of cassava starch based films using tape-casting, *J. Food Eng.* 119 (2013) 800–808. doi:10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2013.07.009.
- [39] P. González-Seligra, L. Guz, O. Ochoa-Yepes, S. Goyanes, L. Famá, Influence of extrusion process conditions on starch film morphology, *LWT - Food Sci. Technol.* 84 (2017) 520–528. doi:10.1016/j.lwt.2017.06.027.
- [40] A. Saralegi, L. Rueda, L. Martin, A. Arbelaiz, A. Eceiza, M.A. Corcuera, From elastomeric to rigid polyurethane/cellulose nanocrystal bionanocomposites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 88 (2013) 39–47. doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.08.025.

- [41] A. Santamaria-Echart, L. Ugarte, A. Arbelaiz, N. Gabilondo, M.A. Corcuera, A. Eceiza, Two different incorporation routes of cellulose nanocrystals in waterborne polyurethane nanocomposites, *Eur. Polym. J.* 76 (2016) 99–109. doi:10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2016.01.035.
- [42] Y.V. García-Tejeda, Y. Salinas-Moreno, F. Martínez-Bustos, Preparation and characterization of octenyl succinylated normal and waxy starches of maize as encapsulating agents for anthocyanins by spray-drying, *Food Bioprod. Process.* 94 (2015) 717–726. doi:10.1016/j.fbp.2014.10.003.
- [43] W. Li, X. Tian, P. Wang, A.S.M. Saleh, Q. Luo, J. Zheng, S. Ouyang, G. Zhang, Recrystallization characteristics of high hydrostatic pressure gelatinized normal and waxy corn starch, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 83 (2016) 171–177. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2015.11.057.
- [44] J. Castaño, R. Bouza, S. Rodríguez-Llamazares, C. Carrasco, R.V.B. Vinicius, Processing and characterization of starch-based materials from pehuen seeds (*Araucaria araucana* (Mol) K. Koch), *Carbohydr. Polym.* 88 (2012) 299–307. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2011.12.008.
- [45] C. Chale, P.J. Halley, R.W. Truss, Mechanical Properties of Starch-Based Plastics, in: P. J. Halley, L. Avérous (Eds.) *Starch polymers, from genetic engineering to green applications*, Burlington, MA: Elsevier, 2014, pp. 187–209.
- [46] K.M. Dang, R. Yoksan, Development of thermoplastic starch blown film by incorporating plasticized chitosan, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 115 (2015) 575–581. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2014.09.005.
- [47] J. González-Gutiérrez, P. Partal, M. García-Morales, C. Gallegos, Effect of processing on the viscoelastic, tensile and optical properties of albumen/starch-based bioplastics, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 84 (2011) 308–315. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2010.11.040.

- [48] N.L. García, L. Ribba, A. Dufresne, M.I. Aranguren, S. Goyanes, Physico-mechanical properties of biodegradable starch nanocomposites physico-mechanical properties of biodegradable starch nanocomposites, *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* 294 (2009) 169–177. doi:10.1002/mame.200800271.
- [49] P. Bertrand, V. Bonnarme, A. Piccirilli, P. Ayrault, L. Lemeé, G. Frapper, J. Pourchez, Physical and chemical assessment of 1,3 Propanediol as a potential substitute of propylene glycol in refill liquid for electronic cigarettes, *Sci. Rep.* 8 (2018) 10702–10711. doi:10.1038/s41598-018-29066-6.
- [50] W.H. Ferreira, C.T. Andrade, Characterization of glycerol-plasticized starch and graphene oxide extruded hybrids, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 77 (2015) 684–690. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2015.09.051.
- [51] L. Lendvai, J. Karger-Kocsis, A. Kmetty, S. X. Drakopoulos, Production and characterization of microfibrillated cellulose-reinforced thermoplastic, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 133 (2015) 42397–42404. doi:10.1002/app.42971.
- [52] A. Jiménez, M.J. Fabra, P. Talens, A. Chiralt, Effect of re-crystallization on tensile, optical and water vapour barrier properties of corn starch films containing fatty acids, *Food Hydrocoll.* 26 (2012) 302–310. doi:10.1016/j.foodhyd.2011.06.009.
- [53] M.A. Bertuzzi, M. Armada, J.C. Gottifredi, Physicochemical characterization of starch based films, *J. Food Eng.* 82 (2007) 17–25. doi:10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2006.12.016.
- [54] R.P. Herrera Brandelero, F. Yamashita, M.V. Eiras Grossmann, The effect of surfactant Tween 80 on the hydrophilicity, water vapor permeation, and the mechanical properties of cassava starch and poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT) blend films, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 82 (2010) 1102–1109. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2010.06.034.

- [55] M.A. Bertuzzi, E.F. Castro Vidaurre, M. Armada, J.C. Gottifredi, Water vapor permeability of edible starch based films, *J. Food Eng.* 80 (2007) 972–978. doi:10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2006.07.016.
- [56] D. Le Corre, A. Dufresne, Starch Nanoparticles: A review, *Biomacromolecules* 11 (2010) 1139–1153. doi:10.1021/bm901428y.
- [57] M. Pirooz, A.H. Navarchian, G. Emtiazi, Antibacterial and structural properties and printability of starch/clay/polyethylene composite films, *J. Polym. Environ.* 26 (2018) 1702–1714. doi:10.1007/s10924-017-1056-8.
- [58] J. Li, M. Zhou, G. Cheng, F. Cheng, Y. Lin, P.X. Zhu, Fabrication and characterization of starch-based nanocomposites reinforced with montmorillonite and cellulose nanofibers, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 210 (2019) 429–436. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2019.01.051.
- [59] D.A. Marín-Silva, S. Rivero, A. Pinotti, Chitosan-based nanocomposite matrices: Development and characterization, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 123 (2019) 189–200. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2018.11.035.
- [60] W. Wang, T. Liang, B. Zhang, H. Bai, P. Ma, W. Dong, Green functionalization of cellulose nanocrystals for application in reinforced poly(methyl methacrylate) nanocomposites, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 202 (2018) 591–599. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2018.09.019.